

C-130 COMPOSITE FLAP DESIGN DEVELOPMENT AND CERTIFICATION

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SUMMARY: The C-130 Composite Flap Programme resulted from the need for redesign of the existing metal flaps which suffer throughout their life from severe acoustic fatigue cracking. The total development programme up to delivery of the first flight set, including static and acoustic fatigue testing, was completed within 12 months. To achieve this ambitious schedule it was necessary to integrate design, manufacturing and certification into a united team with comprehensive understanding of the materials and technologies to be utilised. The C-130J Composite Flap is testimony to this harmonious blend which is so essential to the successful integration of composite material into a production environment.

KEYWORDS: C130 flap, design, development, certification, analysis, manufacturing, testing, integrated product team

INTRODUCTION

The reasons for new C-130J composite flaps can be attributed to associated maintenance problems on older C-130 in-service aircraft. All Hercules aircraft prior to the C-130J model were equipped with centre and outer wing flaps made of aluminium construction with classic rib and thin sheet skins. There has been a large number of reported flap skin cracks from operators over a long period of time. C-130E and C-130H maintenance records showed a high incidence of cracking in flaps and the USAF considered these to be a major maintenance burden on C-130 aircraft. Most of the flap cracks are a result of sonic fatigue in an adverse acoustic environment due to engine propeller wash and exhaust. Corrosion was a lesser contributor, but was also a consideration.

Several new designs were studied as an alternative to the existing aluminium configuration flaps. Different skin gages and materials such as ARALL skins were considered. Carbon fibre/resin composite was selected to be the best and most optimum flap design for the operating conditions.

DESIGN REQUIREMENTS AND SPECIFICATIONS

Most composite marketing is focused on the potential weight savings that can be obtained from extolling the virtues of orthotropic material, however this benefit is usually gained at the expense of manufacturing simplicity. The C-130 composite flaps were not designed for weight efficiency, the composite flap being similar in weight to its metal predecessor. The principal design parameter was durability. The flap had to withstand a very harsh acoustic

environment and the fatigue behaviour of the composite material proved far superior to the aluminium alloy material when used in the conventional skin, spar and rib configuration. In fact, the structural configuration is nothing new and falls into the much maligned description of first generation composite design known as 'black aluminium'. (Refer Fig.1).

Fig. 1: Structural Arrangement - Centre Wing Flap

The re-design required that the flap basic loft contour be retained and the flaps interface with aircraft structure remain the same. The new composite flaps must be structurally and functionally interchangeable with existing metal flaps.

Hawker de Havilland (HdH) was awarded responsibility for the design and build of centre and outer wing flaps using reinforced thermoset resin materials. The separate components were to be mechanically fastened together with titanium, monel and stainless steel fasteners. The flaps must conform to the requirements of Lockheed Martin Aeronautical Systems (LMAS) specifications and standards as well as Federal Aviation Authority (FAA) regulations.

LMAS was responsible for supplying HdH with flap loft contours in CATIA models and all pertinent specifications and standards.

DESIGN BUILD TEAM

The challenge confronting HdH and LMAS was to design and manufacture a set of production flaps for the C-130J within a 12 month time frame of awarding the contract. In order to achieve such a demanding task there had to be full focus on a successful design and build implementation more commonly known these days as Integrated Product Teams (IPT). The seeds for the success of this team were sown by previous programmes at HdH and LMAS. The lessons learnt by HdH on the MD Explorer, Boeing 777 and Boeing 737 IPT, with regard to designer, builder and customer relationships were invaluable to the programme.

Having established a successful tender to win the contract, the goal HdH set itself was to resist the temptation to change the design during the preliminary design phase. HdH despatched 4 designers, 2 manufacturing engineers, 1 analyst/test engineer and 1 acoustic analyst to work on location at LMAS over a 7 week period of concept design. The heavy

emphasis on manufacturing engineering highlighted the focus on a balanced design/build integration. As well as the 'on site' team, the project organisation set up at HdH Bankstown clearly showed the priority and authority that needed to be vested in the project. The acoustic analysis was provided by Vipac Engineers and Scientists Ltd under contract from HdH. The design was consolidated on electronic media using CATIA and NASTRAN and strict discipline applied to ensure the accuracy of the model was at all times preserved. The nickel plated layup mandrels for the skins commenced manufacture during the concept phase with CATIA information sent directly to Express Plastics (UK) for N.C. profiling of the masters. A successful Preliminary Design Review (PDR) allowed the electronic 'model' to be frozen and commencement of Detail Design Phase at HdH.

The Detail Design Phase produced drawings concurrently with the tools. These two operations have traditionally been sequential and the need to parallel the activities required complete trust and close liaison between designer and manufacturer. Also paramount in the success of this phase was the co-location of a LMAS team at HdH. LMAS were the applicant for submission of the design to the certifying authority and therefore worked in unison with HdH to ensure the product met all its specification requirements. The flap design and structural analysis were approved by the LMAS engineering onsite team, including all drawings and reports. Without the onsite team the design, build and delivery of the flaps could not have been accomplished in time for C-130J flight test. The team effort worked extremely well between the two firms and established a healthy on-going relationship which was helpful through the flap installation and flight test programme. This phase was concluded with a successful Critical Design Review (CDR).

With all the tools designed and manufactured and all the drawings released the effort now converted to manufacturing. The design engineers transitioned into development engineers enabling fast resolution of problems and quick response for drawing change.

FAA CERTIFICATION PLAN

As part of the overall C-130J type certification to the FAA regulations, the composite centre and outer wing flaps needed to comply to FAR 25 and advisory circular AC 20-107A. The certification plan for the flaps consisted of:

- Material Qualification Testing
- Submittal of all material and process specifications used in design and manufacture
- Submittal of all engineering drawings
- Submittal of structural analysis
- Structural Qualification Testing

A comprehensive set of design verification tests were conducted on coupons and elements to evaluate specific design details. These tests provided valuable information as part of the design effort. The tests were not part of the formal certification plan since the Structural Qualification tests included all structural features and the effects of critical design conditions. The design verification test results were made available for FAA review.

As certification applicant, LMAS coordinated the certification plans with the local FAA office. Material specifications, process specifications, and engineering drawings were submitted to FAA Designated Engineering Representatives (DER) at LMAS. The structural

analysis was submitted to the DER for recommendation and forwarding to the FAA. Fabrication of material test panels and structural test components at HdH were witnessed by Civil Aviation Safety Authority (CASA) representatives acting under the bilateral FAA/CASA agreement. The Structural Qualification Tests were witnessed by FAA DER's.

COMPOSITE MATERIAL SELECTION, QUALIFICATION AND ALLOWABLES

The selection of materials was an important parameter in keeping manufacturing costs to an acceptable level. Poor choices in this area of design have been the downfall of many promising composite projects in the past.

To meet schedule and cost objectives, the composite material for the C-130 flaps had to meet the following criteria:

- Existing data base and allowables
- Production experience
- FAA approved specifications
- Lower cost relative to newer materials.

LMAS had proposed Hercules AS4-3501-6 carbon/epoxy, however HdH was predominantly using Hexcel's T650/F584 carbon/epoxy materials for MD Explorer and other programmes and proposed using the same material for C-130 Flaps with some cost savings over the use of AS4-3501-6 material. Based on a review of the available T650/F584 data and cost savings, LMAS accepted the use of this material for C-130 Flaps.

For ease of material handleability and fabrication, prepreg plain weave fabric was selected as the material of choice. The qualified material is a solution coated fabric which has excellent drape characteristics.

To allow the use of T650/F584 material on the C-130 Flaps, LMAS developed two new material specifications for tape and fabric materials. These specifications defined all the laminae and laminate material qualification requirements and were approved by the FAA.

All the material qualification work was performed by Hexcel. Hexcel had previously qualified T650/F584 tape and fabric materials for 82°C (180°F) applications to McDonnell Douglas Helicopter Company (MDHC) specifications. This data was FAA approved. Hexcel used this available data and generated additional required data to complete all the data required for LMAS specifications for 104°C (220°F) applications.

All the test panels and test specimens used for generating new data were conformed by FAA-DER who also participated as witness to the qualification testing.

The qualification data was used to adjust the material specification requirements and the design allowables, and then the data and specifications were submitted to the FAA for final approval.

COST EFFECTIVE DESIGN

The HdH proposal based its selection of design concept on its prior experience of the MD Explorer helicopter project. The need was to keep construction simple, there was insufficient development time to steer away from a very conservative approach. To this extent the design

excluded carbon/epoxy tape, honeycomb, film adhesives and secondary bonding. Low cost fasteners were selected that were not necessarily industry standard for this type of construction.

Standardisation of parts and fasteners received heavy focus in the design. Ribs, clips and angles are common wherever possible to minimise different tools. The constant thickness skins and substructure reduced tool complexity and simplified ply layup.

The layup of the material is quasi-isotropic to increase the bi-directional bearing properties and replicate stiffness characteristics of the existing metal flap. Ply drop offs are non existent except where required by material roll width constraints.

Copper foil prepreg was added to the outside surface of the flaps to allow dissipation of lightning strike.

ANALYSIS

Based on the preliminary allowables, the initial analysis of internal loads in critical areas was performed by hand (again due to time constraints) prior to PDR. In parallel, a coarse Finite Element Model (FEM) was developed to assess overall stiffness in bending and torsion and to confirm the internal load distribution. These two activities (hand analysis and coarse FEM) gave a reasonable assurance concerning the structural soundness of the proposed design in a matter of weeks, well before PDR. Factors like thermal expansion of the wing and the forced bending of the flap due to wing deflection were also accounted for at this early stage.

One of the most important components of the analytical side of the project was the use of a fine mesh FEM to determine internal loads and margins of safety. By the time the model was developed, more detailed information concerning wing deflection and the compliance of flap attachment points were available. This information was then included into the model, which was run for all critical load cases. It was noted early in the programme that the amount of information provided by the FEM would not be processed before the scheduled certification activities. For that reason, instead of generating the internal load data, the model was set to provide direct output in terms of safety margins, based on ply by ply analysis performed by NASTRAN. The subsequent practical task was enormously simplified, with a single glance of the strain contour display sufficient to identify hot areas and levels of strain. This automated process provided data output to include directly into the stress reports, without the need to generate safety margins by hand.

Due to the utilisation of blind fasteners (NAS 1919) it was prudent to check the issue of tension loads generated in the fasteners. For this reason, all the parts of the flap were modelled as separate entities and subsequently “sewn” together using Multi-Point Constraint (MPC) elements. This, in turn, enabled direct assessments of tension load in each fastener and the fastener load distribution along the rivetted joint. Consequently, the proper sizing of fastener diameter and pitch in critical areas was determined based on reliable data. The tape with the model data and results was then included in the stress reports.

MANUFACTURING

Extensive producibility and developmental trials were conducted during the pre-manufacturing phase and information constantly fed back into the design.

Minimisation of total parts count was a prime focus of the programme. Innovative production and assembly techniques as well as strict process control are features of the C130 Flap manufacture.

All major tools and assembly jigs were verified and qualified using computer aided theodolite instrumentation which referenced numerical information to the engineering master model data.

TESTING, CERTIFICATION AND FAA INVOLVEMENT

The test programme consisted of three phases:

- Material Qualification Testing (discussed earlier)
- Design Verification Testing
- Structural Qualification Testing.

The Design Verification Tests consisted of elements and coupons to evaluate specific design details. These tests were not part of the formal certification effort. The tests included:

- High cycle fatigue of laminates to evaluate material behaviour in a sonic environment.
- High cycle fatigue of skin/substructure joints.
- Skin panel buckling.
- Skin panel shear strength.
- Skin panel strength with impact damage.
- Skin panel strength after repair.
- Carriage to flap joint.
- Interlaminar tension of substructure angles.
- Fastener pull through.
- Fastener lap shear joint strength.
- Sonic fatigue of flap sections.

Some testing also included elevated temperature and wet environments to simulate the critical design conditions.

The Structural Qualification Tests were conducted on articles representing full scale centre and outer wing flaps. All the structural and loading requirements for the flaps were included in these tests. All full scale static tests were conducted by Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory (AMRL). FAA DER's were involved in the witness of all tests. The tests were:

- Static test of the centre flap.
- Static test of spar and rib components.
- Static test of the outer flap.
- Lightning strike of flap skin.
- Flight testing.

The centre flap static test was conducted under the critical design environment of elevated temperature, wet conditions. Temperature was 93°C (200°F) and the relative humidity was 85%. The flap included Barely Visible Impact Damage (BVID) in the skins at critical

locations. Separately, full scale spar and rib components were tested under the same conditions of elevated temperature, wet environment with impact damage. Results of the test demonstrated that the flap could withstand 225% design limit load without failure.

The outer flap static test was conducted at room temperature, ambient conditions with impact damage. The environmentally compensated test load was applied to account for material strength degradation at environment.

In general, the tests confirmed some important conclusions obtained in the process of FEM analysis. The tension loads in fasteners generated by buckling skin were within safe limits and therefore the use of blind fasteners was justified and overall the correlation between the test and analytical data was excellent.

CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT

In the never ending quest to drive manufacturing costs downwards without compromise to the quality of the product, the following technical innovations are planned for future evaluation:

- Hot Drape Diaphragm Forming (Ribs and Spar).
- Resin Transfer Molding (Ribs)
- Composite Pultrusion (Spars)
- Robot drilling and fastener installation. (Assy).

CONCLUSION

By utilising an Integrated Product Team approach and adopting a schedule which required severe overlapping of traditionally sequential activities HdH and LMAS have achieved technical and commercial success in the design, manufacture and certification of the C-130 composite flaps.

The design criteria for the flaps focused on a robust, cost efficient structure using composite material. This paper confirms that composite structure designed for durability may well have a future market with as much potential as composite structure designed for weight efficiency.